

COMMUNICATION THROUGH THE SLOGANS OF ADVERTISEMENTS A STUDY OF CREATIVE TAGLINES IN INDIAN ADS

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ABSTRACT:- *For flourishing of any business and service advertisement is the most essential part of the marketing strategy. Best product and excellent service can also prove to be meager devoid of ads. Besides the traditional vehicles, Mass media including Newspapers, Magazines, Television, Radio, internet based new media and the digital media are used for carrying the ads as per the requirement in India. It was felt necessary by the researcher to know more as to what stuff in the ad makes it attractive and compel the audiences/ consumers to buy a particular product or avail a specific service even today in 2017? Thus researcher chose to study one of the most important aspect of the ads i.e. Slogans of the advertisers as they form the most important part of any ad. To know the communication through slogans/ Taglines, its creativity and the role, the topic was formulated.*

It is necessary for the advertisers and the ad. agency to know the importance of slogans so as to make their product/ service grab the attention of the people. Similarly the consumers also remember the product or service due to the catchy Slogans. It was found that the Slogans play important part in creating the image of the product or service and increase the business. It was also found during the research that making catchy slogans requires special skills and is not a job of a layman. It was also found that some taglines are so much effective that the audiences remember them but forget the product or service for which they were made. Yet they play most important part in the ads. Many ads make their claims in the form of Slogans. A survey to find the views about the slogans and their impacts showed that it is not possible to think of advertisement without any catchy slogan and that ads without creative slogans fail to do effective business. Various respondents gave different views about the Slogan they liked. It range from the domestic product to FMG, toothpaste, electronics, automobiles, edibles etc. Many opined that few slogans are emotionally attached with them while others remind them of quality and reasonable price. Thus it was found that Slogans are the most important part of the advertisements may they be presented on any media from print, electronic, digital to traditional and folk.

KEY WORDS:- Tagline or strap line, Public interest ads, logo,

INTRODUCTION:- Ad business started flourishing at many places as printing developed in the 15th and 16th century especially after the invention of movable type by **Johann Gutenberg** in 1438 in Germany.¹

In 18th century ads appear in the weekly newspapers in England and since then went on continuously changes in physical format, content, style and the media that carry them².

In India, history of Ads has been a long tradition since the first newspapers published in India in the 19th Century carried advertising.³

According to the **Pitch Madison** Ad Report, the annual turnover in the field of advertisement in India in the **year 2017** is 56152 crore rupees. This size for the glamorous industry is very large.⁴

Advertisements are classified on the basis of various criteria by the people engage in this business. Some of them are [Public service advertising](#), [non-commercial advertising](#), public interest advertising, [cause marketing](#), and [social marketing](#) ads, periodical ads, direct mail ads, classified and display ads etc.⁵

Neil Kokemuller mentions in his literature, ‘Advertisers pay for advertising to accomplish a wide array of goals. Ad objectives generally boil down to long-term branding communication or short-term direct response advertising’.⁶

Paul Suggett says. ‘Advertising has evolved into a vastly complex form of communication, with literally thousands of different ways for a business to get a message to the consumer’.⁷ ‘Advertising can communicate the benefits of a product, generate leads for sales follow-up, build the reputation of a company or compare a company’s products and brands against its competitors’ opines **Ian Linton**.⁸

Advertising includes messages that your company pays for, delivers through a mass medium and uses to persuade consumers. The three general ad objectives are to inform, to persuade and to remind customers. Within these broad goals, companies normally have more specific, quantified objectives, as well.⁹

Any ad has five basic elements in it. They are Headline, visuals or image, body or copy, slogan and logo.¹⁰

Here the study of the Slogans of ads had been carried out by the researcher.

A Slogan is a simple and catchy phrase accompanying a logo or a brand that encapsulates a products appeal or the mission of a firm and makes it more memorable and which is important component of its identification or image. It is also called as catch line, strap line or tag line.¹¹

METHOD:-For this research, the researcher had collected the slogans from various advertisements in Newspapers, magazines, Television and from the Internet sites. Besides studying the literature written by various stalwarts on the topic, the researcher had tried to analyze the slogans of the

advertisements. An experience survey of various veterans, working in the ad world was also made to get an inside to the Research paper. In addition to this a survey of youth consumers of the ads from various categories was carried out to know what they think about the slogans and its relation with ads and whether it has any effect on the buying of product or availing of service on their mind. The survey that was started on **7 June 2017 lasted till 24th** of the month. The respondents were also asked to recall the slogans of few products or services that they use and though hundreds are available, they could not recall even five slogans immediately. Yet they believe that the slogans are essential part of ads accompanied by the visuals. They were asked about their most liked slogan and the percentage of truthful claims and that of the fake claims made in Slogans of various products and services.

COMMUNICATION THROUGH SLOGANS OF INDIAN ADS:- Slogan, strap line, tag line or catch line is an essential part of the advertisement. As said by Ogilvy it should be creative to enhance the sale. If it fails, it is not creative. **Kristen Hamlin** defines ad slogan as ‘A usually a short tagline – less than five words -- that tells potential customers the benefits they can expect when choosing your product or service, or establishes your company brand’.¹²

Highlighting the significance of Slogan **Adam M. Nichols** says that the entire marketing process can be reduced to a single word: strategy. In the world of strategy, or in the realm of marketing, there always crops up the issue of slogans and the appropriate tag lines to deploy in a marketing campaign. Think about it; no product is successfully launched without an accompanying slogan or tag line to aide it. The world’s biggest name in ad industry **David Mackenzie Ogilvy** had mentioned about the creation of slogans of ads saying, ‘The best ideas come as jokes. Make your thinking as funny as possible. I don’t know the rules of grammar. If you’re trying to persuade people to do something, or buy something, it seems to me you should use their language. Consumers buy products whose advertising promises them value for money, beauty, nutrition, relief from suffering, social status and so on.’¹³

Highlighting the creativity in Slogans he says, ‘ If it doesn’t sell, it isn’t creative. What you say in the advertising is more important than how you say it.’¹⁴

Indian bigwig also known as Ad guru Prahlaad Kakkar says, ‘India makes the best advertisements in the world.’¹⁵

He had cited the example of Google India reunion on partition saying, ‘Take the Google India Reunion ad which is based on Partition. Whenever I see it, it brings a lump in my throat. It talks about Partition which Indians and Pakistanis can understand, but it (also) talks about stories.’¹⁶

ANALYSIS OF THE SLOGANS OF ADS :- There are hundreds of advertisements with various slogans and catch lines. For the ease of study, the Researcher had categorized it in various parts to

make the available data precise. The combined analysis was made in this study.

Soft Drinks/ Energy drinks:- In India, the soft drink popularly known as cold drinks, are on for sale round the year in winter and Monsoon too. The proper tool to promote certain features and benefits is your slogan. [A great slogan makes a company or product's benefits clear to the audience.](#)

17

GRAPH 1A:- POPULARITY OF SLOGANS

**A survey carried out in June 2017 showed the following result related to the popularity of slogans among the college youths in Aurangabad city.*

**Slogan Of automobiles-13%, Chocolates-19%, Mobile service providers-23 %, Cold drink and soft drinks-34 %, Soap and detergent slogans- 04%, Fast food- 5% and Television-02%*

POPULARITY OF SLOGANS OF VARIOUS PRODUCTS/SERVICES AMONG THE YOUTHS

The cut throat competition had created war between various brands. They concentrate more or snatching the consumers of other drinks by hooks and crooks. They give strong aggressive slogans. The slogan of coke candidly claims that if anybody wants cold drink it is only Coke and Coca Cola when it says 'Thanda matlab Coca Cola'. Whereas Pepsi claims that its brand is the 'right choice'. Thums up again forwards itself when its slogan appeals to 'Taste the Thunder'. Another soft drink Mountain Dew encourages the youth not to be panicked when it shouts 'Darr kea age jeet hai'. Few orange drinks like Fanta, Maaza, Slice, Seven up are also making tall claims. Maaza and Slice concentrate in slogan on the inclusion of Mango in the drink when Maaza says 'Bottle mey aam,

Maaza hai naam’ and Slice dramatically with Katrina Kaif says ‘Aam Sutr’ which resembles the Indian Sex symbolic slogan Kaamsutr. Sprite counters them all to say ‘ Bujaey pyaas, baaki sab bakwaas’. Energy drinks like Boost ‘Boost is the secret of my energy-our energy, and that of Complian with boy and girl claiming as ‘ I am a complan boy, I am a complain girl’ makes a direct appeal to the children to consume this energy drink.

Slogans of Chocolates and fast food:- Chocolates in India are not only for children but for people of all age including youth and adult. This is the reason why the chocolate ads features slogans for youth and senior adults too. The youth couple is shown consuming various chocolates and slogans for them like Dairy milk says, ‘Swad Zindagi ka’ whereas Kitkat ad also features college going consumers and with the catch line ‘Have a break, Have a kitkat’. Break from work, obviously not for children. ‘Jee lalchaye, raha na jaye’ slogan of Alpenlibe also says something that is mouthwatering. Company slogans have the same objectives as branding. They are phrases that serve as reminders to consumers of why a certain company, product, service or brand is special. Its main goal is to inculcate what a company or product can make or deliver into the minds of viewers.¹⁸

but grownups too. Polo, Mentos, Chloromint are few of the Mint based mouth fresheners showing their own distinct identity like ‘The mint with a hole’ ‘Dimag ki batti jala de’ and ‘ Dobara mat puchna’ are their respective slogans. Here too one will find that they are meant for grownups and not targeted to the children who are in the age of consuming chocolates.

Fast food or junk food is unhealthy food but the western influence on Indian culture had also made Indian youth to opt for fast food as a status symbol and keeping this in mind the fast food businessmen had made umpteen creative slogans to attract the youth and make money out of their fad for the unhealthy stuff. Mc Donald’s have entered the Indian market and are one of the market leaders. Their slogan ‘I’m lovin’it’ had maddened the youths and they go for it as a part of their fashionable life without caring a mole for the negative effect on health. Similarly, KFC, another fast food brand goes, ‘Finger lickin’ good’ which appeals about the taste of this brand. Maggi which is generally prepared at home had its attractive catch line as ‘Taste bhi, Health bhi’ this is about the quality claim where it tells that the product is Tasty as well as healthy so go for it and ignore others. Snickers is also a sort of fast food. It is actually a chocolate filled snack. Earlier they were having the slogan ‘Hungry? Grab a snickers’ but they go on changing it. Here too, the slogan asks a question and replies it. All in four words only. Bingo says ‘No confusion, great combination’ Means it is trying to say that the product has great combination and so do not get confused with any other like product, just consume this. On the other hand Lay’s says, ‘No one can eat just one’. Here the slogan is challenging the taste of the product by saying that one cannot be satisfied on just eating one pouch of Lay’s ruffles.

Slogans of Soaps and detergents:-It is noteworthy that the mega serial on the televisions are called as soap operas or just soaps because the sponsors of such programs were soap manufacturers in large. Thus the competition among variety of soaps and detergent can be understood. Out of this many creative slogans came up as a part of competition to attract the people towards the product. The topmost is Lux which had the slogan for attraction as ‘Beauty bar of film stars’. The manufacturer knows that in India there are two religions, Films and Cricket. Out of these two they selected the FILMSTAR peg to mesmerize the people to purchase their product, the lux. Lifebuoy on the other hand stresses on the health factor saying ‘Lifebuoy hai jaha tandurusti hai waha’. It is emphasizing the need of health rather than other factors. Pearl soap concentrates on the lady beauty with slogan ‘Preparing to be a beautiful lady’. It is said, ‘A **marketing slogan** can play a part in the interplay between rival companies.¹⁹

GRAPH 1 B:- CLAIMS IN THE SLOGANS AND THEIR CREDIBILITY

The youths have given their view about the credibility of the claims and tall claims in the slogan of advertisement of various products and services as follows:-

13 % said that the slogans are genuine, 21 % say the claims are 50 percent true, 27% say that the claims in slogans are less than 50 % true, 34 percent say that the claims are only 25 percent true and 5 percent feel that the claims are totally fake.

VIEWS ABOUT THE CLAIMS IN THE SLOGANS AND THEIR CREDIBILITY

Here they had recognized that women are their customers as they go and purchase the grocery for the home. For this reason the Pearl slogan is attracting the costumer, rather than the consumer. Dettol is another brand that gave the slogan ‘Be 100 percent sure’. Yes the slogan is appealing about the health and claiming to be 100 percent bacteria free. Detergent like Surf Excel with ‘Daag ache hai’ is good one appealing the people to remove the stains with Surf Excel. Nirma is claiming that the bar is tough on washing and does not melt in water. They claim it going for long and washing more clothes in one slogan ‘Nirma Detergent Tikiya - Iski Jhaag Ne Jahu Kar Diya - Paani Mein Rah Kar Bhi Ye Kam Gale Dheron Kapde Dhoye Aur Zyada Chale’, Hamam, Liril, Rexona, Margo ,Santoor, Mysore, Moti, Cinthol, Dove, Medimix are some more with good slogans.

Automobile, Four wheelers and two wheelers:- With indigenous Mahindra, Maruti, Tata and others, dozens of foreign automobile manufacturers in SUV, cars and two wheelers had entered the Indian market with full might in last one decade. While trying to attract the customers they have been giving creative slogans that are many times better than the Indian automobile ads. One thing that was noted during the study was that different vehicles manufactured by same company have different Slogans like Tata safari give- Reclaim your life where as its Indica has- More car per car, Indigo CS had ‘Spoil yourself, Indigo Marina –Big on space, Big on life, Sumo Grande has ‘More than meets the eyes’. All these three slogans are trying to tell the people that their car is big, more spacious and many more. Similarly, Mahindra Scorpio ad slogan says, ‘Nothing else will do’ and Bolero slogan is. ‘Take on anything’. Both slogans include the words that are challenging the customer. Maruti’s Alto had the slogan- Let’s go, Esteem- Welcome to the big world, Grand Vitara- Play it yourself. These slogans seem to counter the slogans of foreign made cars. The foreign collaborated Hyundai also had many attractive slogans, Santro Xing of this company had- The sunshine car, Sonata Embera- Undoubtedly distinguished, Tucson- Your Spirit of adventure AND – makes every day an adventure, Verna of Hyundai had two word slogan that says- Feel it. Here too, it can be seen that they company is trying to say that their product is distinguished and adventurous. At one place it is emotionally appealing the car when it says-Feel it.

Two wheeler Pulsar brand of Bajaj is made for male as is evident from its slogan- Definitely Male whereas Hero Honda, Indian company in collaboration with Japanese company is telling Indians that Their bike is- Desh ki dhadkan. Again, emotional appeal. The use of slogans may be examined in so far as the slogans continue unconscious and unintentional responses.²⁰

Splendor bike of Honda is taking the slogan a different way. It is urging the Indians to buy the bike claiming that it is most economical when it says- Fill it, Shut it, forget it. Means you have to forget filling of petrol for long. Suzuki Hayate is claiming that it is multi specialty bike when their slogan hits the ear- Suzuki Hayate, yuhi nahi chalute. TVS company had one of its bike Victor with slogan- More smiles per hour. Enticer brand of Yamaha says- Blue blooded Yamaha. These slogans are countering the competitors and appealing the youths to purchase their bikes.

In similar fashion there are ads with creative slogans related to ISP like Nokia- Connecting people, Idea- An idea can change your life, Airtel- Expressing yourself etc and other service sector slogans like that of ICICI bank- Hum hai na, HSBC- The world's local bank, HDFC- Jiyo sar uthat ke, etc. The slogans of these banks also seem competing amongst themselves for snatching the consumers towards them. One is trying to give the consumers an assurance that they are their for your help whey it says Ham hai na. HSBC i.e. Hong Kong Shanghai banking corporation known that

it is a foreign bank and so for alluring Indians it had the slogan – World’s local bank whereas HDFC is telling people that if they do business with the bank, they can live with prestige- Jiyo sar utha ke. its identification or image. It is also called as catch line, strap line or tag line.¹¹

CONCLUSION : Slogans are inseparable form of ad content and they help the people keep the product in mind for a longer time. If the slogans are more creative, they are more in the memory and during the buying of goods or availing the services, the brand and ultimately the corporate house manufacturing the good or providing the service is benefitted. Some slogans are so much creative that people remember the Slogan but unfortunately forget the product e.g. A ‘pen’ without ‘pain’ or A ‘tire’ that does not ‘tires’ referred to JK Tires. Now many such effective slogans are withdrawn from the Advertisements because though people remember them, they forget the brand and it is of no use for the Manufacturer. There are many slogans which are stressing the name of their product or service once or twice so as to emphasize on the product or service rather than Slogan without the name of product. During the research it was found that some companies of similar products prepare slogans as a part of ‘Ad war’ not for impressing and compelling the buyer towards their product but for countering the Ad of the competitor.

It was found in a survey during the research that the respondents, mostly youths, like the slogans of the Soft drinks the most. 34 percent gave their opinion in favor of such slogans whereas 23 % respondents like the slogans of Mobile service providers. Least liked slogans were found to be that of fast foods(4%) and the worst 2% was that of Television channels. 34 percent of the youths say that the claims is slogans are not more than 25 percent reliable whereas 27 % say that tall claims through the slogans of advertisements are not more than 50 percent credible. Only 13 percent believe that the slogans are genuine and 5 percent feel that they are totally fake and misleading.

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